

THE IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY SKILLS OF TEACHER STUDENTS

Dr.Naik Tarsing B.

Assistant Professor

S.M.T .Govt. College of Education, Kolhapur.

Abstract :

Information communication technology skills and emotional intelligence are new and emerging trends in teacher education. This paper to examine the impact of emotional intelligence on information communication technology skills of teacher students in Government college of education, Ratnagiri Maharashtra. Researcher have consider the information communication technology skills, emotional intelligence and teacher students thoughts and way of thinking. The main objective of the study was to test the impact of emotional intelligence on Information communication technology skills of prospective teacher students. The training institution is concerned with the development of teacher students in all round development of his physical, social and emotional, teaching knowledge, skills, and personality qualities. A sample out of 50 student teachers 35 participants randomly selected from Government B. Ed. College Ratnagiri was used. Data analysis was done by using standard deviation and t-values. Findings of the study showed that overall emotional intelligence score was positively impact with the information communication technology skill of student teachers.

Key words :

Information communication technology skills, Student Teacher emotional intelligence .

Introduction:

Emotional intelligence is an important element to student teachers attendance and punctuality, teacher educators attitude and methodology in teaching, teaching-learning process, teacher students performance and student teacher feedback, student educator and students teacher to determine competencies in student teachers information communication technology skills . Emotional emphasized the importance of handling emotions as mechanisms in handling success in life. Academic performance success in life is related to students' role in higher learning institution. Students have to prepare themselves after graduating for the purpose of entering the job market. The question on how will they be able to master the communication and information technology skills depend on their level of emotional intelligence. In emotional intelligence, the important qualities which should be taken into consideration to improve skills in communication and information technology can be related to self-conscious, self-motivation, impulse control, information communication technology skills.

Related Literature to Emotional Intelligence :-

1. Hossein Jenaabadi (2014) : conducted a study on studying the relation between emotional intelligence and self-esteem with academic achievement. The results showed that emotional intelligence and self-esteem of students had no effect on their academic achievement. The self-esteem of female students was higher than male students.

2. Turkey Nuri Tok et al (2013) : Conducted a study on the relationship between emotional intelligence and classroom management approaches of primary school teachers. The results revealed that emotional intelligence was a positive predictor of teacher-centered classroom management with weak predictive power. There was a low-level, positive, and significant relationship between emotional intelligence and classroom management approaches of primary school teachers. The emotional intelligence significantly predicts student centered classroom management. There was a positive significant relationship between primary school teachers' in their student centered classroom management approach.

3. Adina Ignat (2012): Conducted a study on *teachers'* satisfaction with life, job satisfaction and their emotional intelligence. The results showed some differences between teachers' work mentality, satisfaction with life and general job satisfaction in terms of emotional intelligence level. The emotional intelligence of teachers was correlated with a positive attitude towards work and satisfaction with life.

4. Sander Sara (2011) : Conducted a study on emotional intelligence, job satisfaction and students' perceptions of the quality of online adjust faculty. The results did not show a significant correlation between emotional intelligence and longitudinal teaching measures used to measure faculty quality. A moderate positive correlation between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction was revealed.

5. Hadi Kajbaf Nezhad (2011) : Conducted a study on the relationship between mental skills and emotional intelligence in athlete girls' students. The findings showed that there were relationship between psychological skills and emotional intelligence. It exhibits the significant and positive relationship between psychological skills and emotional intelligence.

6. Irudhayamary (2014): Conducted a study on emotional intelligence and quality of life among high school teachers. The findings revealed that there were significant differences between male and female high school teachers in their level of emotional intelligence. There were significant differences between male and female high school teachers in their level of quality of life. There were significant association between quality of life and emotional intelligence of high school teachers.

7. Caroline (2013): Conducted a study on modernity and emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between modernity and emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students. There was a significant relationship between modernity and emotional intelligence of female B.Ed. students.

8. Samir Kumar Lenka (2012): conducted a study on emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers in relation to their professional development. The findings showed that there was a significant difference between emotional intelligence of male and female secondary school teachers. There was a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and professional development of secondary school teachers. There was a significant difference between the level of emotional intelligence are very high or very low in teachers of secondary school.

8.Sandhya U. Samudre (2012): conducted a study on a comparative study of emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students. The finding showed that there was no significant difference in emotional intelligence among rural and urban B.Ed. students on all nine factors out of ten dimensions namely self-awareness, empathy, self-motivation, emotional stability, managing relations, integrity, self-development, commitment and altruistic behavior. No difference was found in the overall emotional intelligence among rural and urban students.

9.Deepa (2012): conducted a study on influence of emotional intelligence and thinking styles on decision making skills of distance education B.Ed. students. The study revealed that the factor analysis yields a single factor with considerate factor loading. The factor for the study had been identified as cognitive self-manage decision making. The factor was explained in terms, relationship management, emotional intelligence, thinking styles and decision making skills. There was significant influence of emotional intelligence on decision making skills. There were a significant influence on emotional intelligence and thinking styles on decision making skills of the distance education B.Ed. students.

Consider that teacher education institution student teachers succeed in impact of emotional intelligence on information communication technology skills In particular, interested in knowing to what extent the use of new technologies affect the information communication technology skills and the emotional intelligence domain.

Objectives:

- 1.To compare the emotional intelligence and information communication technology skills of student teachers.
- 2.To study the student teacher attitude towards emotional intelligence and information communication technology skills.
- 3.To study the emotional intelligence and information communication technology skills student teachers.
2. To know the correlation between emotional intelligence and information communication technology skills Student teachers.
3. To study the Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. student teachers in context of their faculty.

Research Sample-

For the present study the purposive sampling method was used for the selection of the sample consisted at Government College of Education, Ratnagiri. The Details of Sample results as follows

Table 1: Sampling data

Total	Data for emotional intelligence and information communication technology skills
50	33

Table 1 shows that out of 50 students 33 were selected for Data for emotional intelligence and information communication technology skills at the B. Ed. colleges. The percentage of selected data is 66% .

Research Method :

All indications, student teachers are immersed in the culture of new technologies. However, as noted earlier, this new dynamic of interaction has been transferred to the classroom with the help of information communication technology. This is a emotional intelligence and information communication technology skills in computer system where, in addition to link tasks, assessment tasks, there are windows of interaction of the type chat, forum, e-mail.

The emotional intelligence was measure with the help of scales were Interpersonal Scale consists of 10 items, Stress Management Scale consists of 8 items, Adjustment Scale consists of 7 items, General Mood Scale consists of 10 items and Positive Impression Scale-Control Scale consists of 6 items. High scores indicate high emotional intelligence level while low scores indicate low emotional intelligence level. Communication skills were measured using scales by interpersonal communication skills 6 items, High scores indicate high communications skills while low scores indicate low communications skills. Information Technology Skills Information technology skills were measured based on instrument by Computer Self-Efficacy Scale.

Conclusion and Results: The teacher-students come into the profession and as existing teachers learn more and develop new ideas. Moment Correlation analysis was employed to examine the degree of relationship between emotional intelligence, communication skills and information technology skills. Emotional intelligence, and information communication technology skills are complementary components. They are sometimes perceived as important but not taken as needs when discussing graduates quality. Consideration for balancing between academic performance and these competencies are not being taken seriously. Paper qualifications are everything compare to self asset which actually is the passport for success. The implication of all this is the birth and production of graduates who are excellence in academic but poor in emotional intelligence, communications skills and information technology skills. Activities such as workshops on improving students' soft skills such as emotional intelligence skills, communication skills and information technology skills need to be integrated in co-curricular activities. Although the activities are sometimes run by universities and student bodies, the importance of these skills in relations to preparation towards entering job market should be stressed. Students need to be told and justify regarding why it is so important to have high level skills. This will enable them to survive in the real world when they graduated. In other words, public universities should bear the social responsibility of producing a more balanced and quality student teachers .

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